

White Paper — QUBIC

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Abstract

QUBIC (Q&U Bolometric Interferometer for Cosmology) is an experiment designed to measure the polarization of the cosmic microwave background (CMB), the relic radiation from the Big-Bang. Detailed measurements of tiny temperature anisotropies in the CMB shaped our understanding of the early Universe. Accurate measurements of its polarization may reveal even earlier features, in particular the presence of gravitational waves with primordial origin. Such measurements can probe inflationary cosmological models, which postulate that quantum effects during an accelerated expansion at the earliest stages after the Big-Bang produced gravitational waves along with the density fluctuations that later seeded galaxy formation. QUBIC will join other international efforts currently pursuing this goal using a novel approach, which combines the sensitivity of bolometric detectors with the control of systematic effects provided by interferometry. After its current calibration phase is completed a technological demonstrator already constructed in European laboratories will be deployed in Alto Chorrillos, a site in the Puna near San Antonio de los Cobres, Salta, Argentina. The complete first module of the instrument is planned to be installed during 2020. We review the scientific goals of the project, the instrument design and its expected performance.

1 Scientific Context

The oldest light in the Universe is the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) radiation, discovered by Penzias and Wilson in 1965 [1]. It has a thermal distribution with a temperature of 2.725 K. It brings us information about the conditions in the Universe almost 14 billion years ago, when no planets, stars or galaxies had yet formed. This was the time, 380,000 years after the Big-Bang, when the Universe had expanded enough so that the CMB temperature dropped down to the point that electrons and protons could combine into neutral atoms, from which photons scatter much less efficiently than from free electrons. The CMB photons bring us a picture of the Universe at such early times.

Tiny variations in the temperature of the CMB that arrives from different directions in the sky have been measured with increased precision since 1992 [2]. They are interpreted as the manifestation of small primordial inhomogeneities in the matter density that acted as seeds for the formation of galaxies and other large scale structures in the Universe. Their measurement allows a high-precision determination of the parameters of the current cosmological model [3].

The CMB was predicted to be linearly polarized [4]. The polarization was imprinted by anisotropic Thomson scattering during the last few interactions of CMB photons with free electrons, a process somewhat similar to how light is polarized after reflection off a surface. This small effect was experimentally verified for the first time in 2002 by the Degree Angular Scale Interferometer (DASI), located at the South Pole [5]. The process that imprinted the polarization was mostly driven by density inhomogeneities, responsible also for most of the CMB anisotropy. Gravitational waves can also leave their imprint in the CMB polarization [6, 7, 8]. A method was devised to disentangle what fraction of the polarization originates from gravitational waves [9, 10]. It is based upon a decomposition of the polarization properties into E -modes, invariant under reflections, and B -modes, that change sign under a reflection. Scalar (density) fluctuations at first order generate E -modes only, while tensor (gravitational waves) fluctuations can produce both. The E -modes are much larger than the expected B -modes, and have been measured with increasing accuracy since 2002, providing further confirmation of the Big-Bang paradigm and increasing the precision on the determination of cosmological parameters. On the contrary, B -modes imprinted by gravitational waves have not been observed yet.

B -modes in the CMB polarization have been observed at relatively small angular scales, of the order of a few arc minutes [11, 12]. These B -modes were predicted to exist as a consequence of weak gravitational lensing, the distortion of photon trajectories away from the straight line in an inhomogeneous gravitational field. Gravitational lensing rotates primordial E -modes into B -modes [13]. Measurement of these "secondary" B -modes is a great accomplishment, since an accurate mapping of the lensing effect provides insight into the distribution of dark matter on large scales, and may even allow an indirect measurement of the mass of the neutrinos.

Primordial B -modes, with an amplitude that is expected to peak at an angular scale of the order of one degree, are searched for with great expectation, since they would be indirect evidence for the existence of gravitational waves with cosmological wavelengths, that can not be detected directly with current instruments such as the Laser Interferometer Gravitational-Wave Observatory (LIGO) [14]. Primordial gravitational waves would be produced during an inflationary phase in the expansion of the early Universe. Inflation is currently the dominant paradigm to understand why the energy-density in the Universe is so close to the critical value corresponding to spatial-flatness, and why otherwise causally-disconnected regions when the CMB photons decoupled have almost the same temperature today [15, 16, 17]. It also provides a mechanism to generate tiny perturbations in the matter density that much latter seed galaxy formation. This same mechanism generates primordial gravitational waves, but inflationary models do not make a definite prediction for their amplitude, and consequently for the amplitude of the signal in B -modes. Observation of the footprint of gravitational waves in the B -modes of the CMB poses a great experimental challenge, partly due to their likely minuscule amplitude and also because their signature can be contaminated with polarized foregrounds of galactic origin.

Several experimental efforts are currently pursuing the search for primordial B -modes. Some are located at the South Pole [18, 19], that offers the driest site in the world and hence the best atmospheric conditions for the task. Others are in the Atacama desert in Chile [20, 21, 22, 23], the second driest site on Earth. We review in this article the QUBIC project [24, 25, 26, 27, 28], that will soon join the search for primordial B -modes from the Puna in Salta, Argentina. QUBIC is a novel kind of instrument, that combines the sensitivity of bolometric detectors based on Transition-

Edge Sensors [29] with the control of systematics granted by interferometric operation.

This white paper is an summary of the information contained in a review in press [30] and in the QUBIC Technical Report [27].

2 Objectives

Linear polarization is typically described in terms of Stokes parameters Q and U , that can be expanded in spherical harmonics with spin 2 [31]:

$$(Q \pm iU) = \sum_{\ell m} a_{\ell m}^{(\pm 2)} Y_{\ell m}^{(\pm 2)} . \quad (1)$$

Alternatively E and B -modes are defined through the linear combinations [9, 10]

$$\begin{aligned} a_{\ell m}^E &= -(a_{\ell m}^{(+2)} + a_{\ell m}^{(-2)})/2 \\ a_{\ell m}^B &= -(a_{\ell m}^{(+2)} - a_{\ell m}^{(-2)})/2i . \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

E -modes are parity invariant, while B -modes change sign under a parity transformation. Characterization of CMB polarization properties in terms of E and B -modes is an invaluable source of information on different physical processes at work in the early Universe. B -modes can be used as a probe to infer if primordial gravitational waves drove partially the process that imprinted the polarization, in addition to density fluctuations. The origin of this possibility is illustrated in figure 1. Linear polarization can be imprinted in the CMB through Thomson scattering by electrons if the radiation has a quadrupolar anisotropy. The imprinted pattern of linear polarization differs depending on the type of motion of the electrons that scatter the radiation. Density waves produce a linear gradient in the gravitational potential that drives the motion of electrons, rotationally symmetric around the wave direction. Gravitational waves instead distort the gravitational potential differently in orthogonal directions perpendicular to their direction of propagation. The figure illustrates these different patterns in the rest frame of an electron. Shown also is the final polarization pattern after superposition of three crossing plane waves. Density waves do not imprint B -modes, while gravitational waves do.

Figure 1: Illustration of polarization patterns induced by density waves compared to those by gravitational waves. Reproduced from [32].

The major concern for contamination of a signal of primordial B -modes in addition to instrumental systematic effects are astrophysical foregrounds, particularly polarization by dust grains aligned by the galactic magnetic field and also synchrotron emission by relativistic electrons. They can in principle be accounted for through their angular power spectra and frequency dependence, distinct from that of the CMB. Measurements of CMB polarization at several frequencies are crucial for disentangling astrophysical foregrounds.

2.1 Quantum effects during inflation

An inflationary period in the early Universe [15, 16, 17] may have been the source for the tiny perturbations in the matter density that much later seeded galaxy formation. Inflation can both generate quantum fluctuations and also drive them to cosmological scales. All fields have quantum fluctuations in their vacuum state. Quantum fluctuations at small scales in the field ϕ that drives the inflationary expansion are stretched to cosmological wavelengths and transferred to the matter density as inhomogeneities at later stages, when the expansion is radiation or matter-dominated. The wavelength of the fluctuations is expanded by a factor larger than 10^{30} during inflation, which explains their cosmological size in spite of their quantum origin. Their amplitude is almost the same when their wavelength is comparable to the cosmological horizon. The fluctuations in the field ϕ driving inflation and those in gravitational waves h have the same quantum origin and have comparable amplitude, determined by the value H of the Hubble constant (the rate of expansion) during the inflationary phase:

$$\langle h^2 \rangle = \frac{GH^2}{2\pi} \quad \text{with} \quad H^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3}V(\phi) \implies \langle h^2 \rangle = \frac{V(\phi)}{M_{\text{Planck}}^4}, \quad (3)$$

where G is Newton's constant, and $M_{\text{Planck}} \approx 10^{19}$ GeV is Planck's mass. The relative intensity between the tensor and scalar fluctuations predicted by inflation is typically described in terms of the dimensionless quantity r :

$$r = \frac{\langle h^2 \rangle}{\langle (\delta\rho/\rho)^2 \rangle}. \quad (4)$$

Here $\delta\rho/\rho$ are the relative density fluctuations, which are very well characterized by measurements of temperature anisotropies, and are of the order of 10^{-5} . This is why a measurement of r (the tensor-to-scalar ratio) is so relevant. It would reveal the presence of primordial gravitational waves, and determine the energy scale (the potential V) at which inflation took place:

$$V^{1/4} \approx \left(\frac{r}{0.01} \right)^{1/4} (10^{16} \text{ GeV}). \quad (5)$$

Measurement of r would also provide additional insight into the shape of the potential driving inflation, not only its absolute scale [33].

2.2 Bounds on primordial gravitational waves

In 2014 the BICEP2 experiment, located just next to where DASI measured E -modes for the first time in 2002, made the first detection of B -modes in the sky at degree angular scales [34], compatible with a value $r = 0.2$. It did so with an instrument operating at 150 GHz and scanning a region of the sky in which the galactic contamination was expected to be negligible. Subsequent measurements and analysis, in particular correlating data from BICEP2 and Keck Array at 150 GHz with that from the Planck satellite at 353 GHz, revealed [35] that the excess of B -modes observed at large angular scales was dominated by polarized emission by galactic dust. Figure 2 displays in the left panel the 95% confidence level upper limits for B -mode power from different CMB experiments with no significant detections (as compiled in the NASA-LAMBDA site <https://lambda.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). Data from ACTPol, BICEP1, BOOMERanG, CAPMAP, CBI, DASI, MAXIPOL, QUaD, QUIET-Q, QUIET-W, and WMAP are included. Plotted is the rotationally invariant angular power spectrum $C_\ell^{BB} = \frac{1}{2\ell+1} \sum_m a_{\ell m}^{B*} a_{\ell m}^B$ for the B -modes. The corresponding angular scale in terms of the multipole moment is about $1^\circ(180/\ell)$. As reference theoretical predictions in a Λ CDM cosmology with values of the tensor-to-scalar ratio $r = 0.1$ (gray) and $r = 0.01$ (blue) are shown. The dashed lines are the tensor contributions and the solid lines are the total power after addition of the expected signal from weak gravitational lensing of E -modes (gray dotted line). Note that the signal in B -modes from primordial gravitational waves peaks at degree angular scales ($\ell \approx 80$) while that of lensing of E -modes peaks at significantly smaller angular scales ($\ell \approx 1000$). A reionization bump is also predicted for the tensor modes at larger angular scales ($\ell < 10$). The right panel of figure 2 displays the B -mode power measured by experiments with significant detections. Results from BICEP2, Planck, POLARBEAR, and SPTpol are included. The BICEP2 + Keck data points show the CMB contribution after separation into CMB, dust, and synchrotron components. The BICEP2 + Keck/Planck data points

Figure 2: Left: 95% CL upper limits for the angular power spectrum in B -modes from different CMB experiments with no significant detections. Shown separately are the theoretical predictions for the contribution from lensing of E -modes (gray dotted line) and from primordial gravitational waves for $r = 0.1$ (gray dashed) and $r = 0.01$ (blue dashed lines). The solid lines correspond to the total power expected for $r = 0.1$ (gray) and $r = 0.01$ (blue). Right: observed B -modes from CMB experiments with significant detections. The lensing of E -modes into B -modes is detected with high significance, and at 95% confidence level $r < 0.06$. Figures reproduced from NASA-LAMBDA, <https://lambda.gsfc.nasa.gov/>.

show results with dust foreground subtraction based on measured cross-power between Planck and BICEP2 + Keck. The other points show results without any foreground subtraction.

The signal expected from rotation of E -modes into B -modes by weak gravitational lensing is detected with high significance, and at 95% confidence level the tensor-to-scalar ratio is currently bound to be $r < 0.06$ [36], which already disfavours the simplest inflationary models of the early Universe.

The quest for detection of primordial B -modes in the CMB continues to be a major experimental challenge. Accurate foreground contamination and removal of lensing effects for values as low as $r = 0.001$ are challenging, but potentially feasible [37].

In what follows we describe the approach taken by QUBIC to confront the challenge of measuring primordial B -modes.

3 Methodology

3.1 The QUBIC instrument

QUBIC is an additive interferometer formed by different components, as schematized in figure 3. The detection system is contained inside a cryostat that is cooled down to 4K using pulse-tubes. The microwave signals to be measured enter the cryostat through a 45 cm diameter window made of ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene [38] that provides excellent transmission and mechanical stiffness. After the window, filters ensure a low thermal load inside the cryostat. Following this are a rotating Half-Wave-Plate (HWP) that modulates the polarization, and then a polarizing grid that selects one of the two linear polarization components.

Right below the polarizing grid an array of 400 corrugated horns receives the incoming radiation and defines the baselines for the interferometric operation of the instrument. These primary horns are followed by secondary back-horns that re-emit the signal towards an optical combiner constituted of a dual-mirror system. This combiner allows the radiation coming from different directions to sum coherently in the various locations of the detector focal planes, thus producing the interference fringes pattern. A key part of QUBIC is an array of switches placed between the two feed-horn arrays, which can be used to exclude particular baselines when the instrument operates in self-calibrating mode, as described in section 3.4.1.

Figure 3: Schematics of the QUBIC instrument. Figure reproduced from [24].

Between the mirrors and the focal planes a dichroic filter splits the signal into its 150 GHz and 220 GHz sub-bands, imaged onto orthogonal focal planes, each equipped with 1024 Transition-Edge-Sensors (TES) cooled down to 320 mK. Of the set of 1024 TES, 992 are exposed to the sky radiation, while the rest are used to characterize systematic effects. The sensors are read using a cryogenic readout system based on superconducting quantum interference devices (SQUIDS) and Si-Ge application-specific integrated circuits (ASIC) operating at 4K with an unprecedented multiplexing factor equal to 128 [39, 40].

The TES technology is well developed and extensively used in several millimetric and sub-millimetric astronomical experiments. They have been chosen as detectors for the QUBIC first module. Other types of detectors such as Kinetic Inductance Detectors (KIDs) [41] will be considered for future QUBIC modules as they may offer an easier fabrication and readout, and larger scalability.

QUBIC will host two arrays of bolometric detectors, operating respectively at 150 GHz and 220 GHz, that will observe interference fringes formed by the back-to-back horns on the focal planes of the optical combiner. The image formed is the result of the interference from the sum of the fields emitted by each of the 400 apertures.

Interferometry offers an improved control of instrumental systematics with respect to direct imaging, because interference fringes from different baselines can be calibrated individually. This feature is made possible in QUBIC thanks to the electromagnetic shutters inserted between the primary and secondary horns. Each shutter consists of a blade operated by a solenoid magnet that can slide into a smooth circular waveguide, and acts as a RF switch.

In the self-calibration mode, pairs of horns are successively shut when observing an artificial partially polarized source. QUBIC will use for external self-calibration a source able to radiate a typical power of few mW through a feedhorn with a well-known beam, and a low level of cross-polarisation, typically less than -30 dB. The source is a microwave synthesizer operated around 10 GHz followed by a multiplication chain which brings the frequency in the millimeter wave range to generate quasi-monochromatic signals in both QUBIC frequency bands. This external calibration source will be located in the far-field of the interferometer, at about 40 m from the instrument and it will be mounted on top of a tower near the instrument shelter inside an insulation box suitable to maintain the device within a specified temperature range. In addition, two carbon fiber sources located inside the cryostat, just next to the array of back-to-back horns and switches, will also be used for calibration purposes [42].

The QUBIC instrument is currently in a phase of laboratory calibration of its so-called ‘‘Technological Demonstrator’’ (TD). The TD uses the cryostat and 1K box built for the first module, but has a reduced focal plane and horn array and a smaller optical combiner compared to the full instrument. The TD has one-quarter of the TES focal plane (i.e. 256 pixels) operating at 150 GHz and 64 back-to-back horns with their respective switches.

A more detailed description of the QUBIC instrument can be found in its Technical Design Report in [27]. The QUBIC instrument is being built by an international collaboration with participating laboratories in France, Italy, UK, Ireland, USA and Argentina.

3.2 The Alto Chorrillos site

The QUBIC instrument will be deployed in Alto Chorrillos, Salta, Argentina ($24^{\circ} 11'11.7''$ S, $66^{\circ} 28'40.8''$ W) at 4,870 meters above the sea level, in what is known as the Puna de Atacama region. This location is 180 km away from the Chajnantor site in Chile where other millimeter-wave experiments and observatories are located (ALMA, APEX, Advanced ACTPol, POLARBEAR and CLASS) and offers similar atmospheric properties [43, 27]. It is next to the location of the Large Latin American Millimeter Array (LLAMA), a bi-lateral cooperation project between Argentina and Brasil that is installing a 12 m radiotelescope operating at millimeter and submillimeter wavelengths. This location has been characterized during several years within the framework of the site selection process for the Cherenkov Telescope Array project, and for the LLAMA project, which has atmospheric requirements similar to those of QUBIC.

Several developments related to the site are ongoing, mainly devoted to preparations to test the instrument upon arrival to Argentina and to secure its installation in Alto Chorrillos. The access road to the LLAMA site and from there to the QUBIC site has already been built, and constructions towards the installation of the first module are under way.

3.3 Detection and analysis chain

3.3.1 Signal model and synthesized beam

The image that QUBIC will observe in each of the two focal planes is the result of an interferometric pattern that arises from the superposition of the signals of each of the secondary antennas in the horn array.

As more and more horns are open in the observing array, the number of baselines increases (a baseline is the vector separating two horns). The constructive and destructive superposition of the re-emitted signals produces an effective beam which is highly non-trivial. In fact, the synthesized beam of QUBIC has a complicated shape, with a central peak and replications. The beam can be approximated by a central gaussian with secondary gaussian peaks, separated by an angular distance of about 8.5° with a width equal to the full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) at the observing frequency. Both the separation distance between peaks and their width depend on the frequency of the received signal. In the left panel of figure 4, a schematic plot of the synthesized beam for two monochromatic frequencies is shown, where it is clear the dependence on the observing frequency of the separation between primary and secondary peaks. The amplitudes of the primary and secondary peaks are modulated by a gaussian which is equal to the primary beam of the input horn. For a finite bandwidth, the beam is computed as the superposition of all the monochromatic beams included in the band, and due to the dependence on the frequency, the secondary peaks appear asymmetric and elongated. In the right panel of Figure 4 we show the synthesized beam of the central pixel, considering a 30% bandwidth.

3.3.2 Map-making

QUBIC will observe a partial area of the sky, similar to the region observed by the BICEP2 Collaboration (another observational effort to measure the primordial B-modes [34]). It is a region with relatively low galactic foregrounds, although they cannot be neglected. This is the main reason why the instrument has two frequency bands, and the relevance of the spectro-imaging properties of QUBIC, which will be described in subsection 3.4.2. The contamination from foregrounds can be alleviated when the sky is observed in several frequencies.

When the signal is an extended region in the sky, as the QUBIC area will be, every detector in the focal plane will receive the signal from different directions in the sky, due to the non-trivial shape of the synthesized beam.

Exactly in the same way as for a usual imager, we can scan the sky with our synthesized beam with any scanning strategy, and any individual measurement results in the convolution of the sky through our synthesized beam. From the Time-Ordered Data (TOD) of each individual bolometer, we can reconstruct a map of the sky, taking into account the special shape of the synthesized beam.

Figure 4: Left panel: Synthesized beam for the monochromatic case, for two nearby frequencies. The separation between the primary and secondary peaks of the beam depends on the frequency of the signal. Right panel: Simulation of the synthesized beam of the center pixel of the 150 GHz array, taking into account the finite (30%) bandwidth of the detectors. The addition of all of the secondary peaks of the monochromatic beams included in the band results on secondary peaks which are asymmetric and elongated. Figure adapted from [24] and [28].

3.4 Calibration and expected performance

3.4.1 Self-calibration

The design of QUBIC as a bolometric interferometer allows the exploitation of redundant interferometric patterns to control and reduce the systematics of the experiment. By using different combinations of open horns in the array, we can obtain a number of redundant baselines that can be used to self-calibrate the instrument. This technique is derived from radio-interferometry self-calibration [44].

To understand the basic concept of self-calibration, it is important to note that the interference pattern produced by two open horns will be exactly the same as one obtained with a different pair of open horns but defining exactly the same baseline (separation and orientation of the pair of open horns). For an ideal instrument, with no systematic effects, the interferometric pattern depends only on the baseline. Hence, we can use the observations obtained with equivalent baselines to account for the systematics of the instrument, by analysing the differences observed with different but equivalent baselines. The theoretical framework of the self-calibration procedure is described in detail in [45].

Systematic errors can come in the form of horn location errors, pointing errors, asymmetries of beams, bolometer location errors, diagonal, and so forth. Due to the time modulation of the polarized signal given by the HWP, and the subsequent action of the interference array, for a real instrument, there is the possibility of a leakage from Q to U and vice versa, due to uncertainties and errors in the process. Therefore, there will be a leakage between the E and B -modes, in particular from E to B (the original B -mode is expected to be much lower than the E -mode, hence the leakage from B to E might be neglected). We can further give a constraint to the induced value of the tensor-to-scalar ratio r . The leakage from E -modes to B -modes is significantly reduced by applying the self-calibration. During the self-calibration phase, pairs of horns are successively shut while QUBIC observes an artificial partially-polarized source (a microwave synthesizer) in the far field. Then, the signal measured by each individual pair of horns is reconstructed and compared with each other. If the source is stable, then redundant baselines correspond to the same mode of the observed field, and therefore, a different signal between them can only be due to photon noise or instrumental systematic effects.

In Figure 5 we show the improvement in the power spectrum estimation with self-calibration, depending on the time spent in the calibration mode. The more time spent in self-calibration mode, the lower the E to B leakage due to instrumental imperfections. In black solid lines, the prediction of the B -mode polarization power spectrum is displayed, for different values of the tensor-to-scalar ratio r .

Figure 5: Improvement in the recovery of the B -mode power spectrum as a function of the time spent in the self-calibration mode. Figure reproduced from [28], adapted from [45].

3.4.2 Spectral imaging

The particular shape of the synthesized beam of the QUBIC experiment enables a peculiar and most convenient use of the instrument: that of a spectro-imager. Indeed, the dependence of the angular distance between primary and secondary peaks of the beam on the frequency of the observed signal allows the separation of the signal into different subfrequencies inside each channel, providing information at more frequency bands than originally designed for. In this way, we can count on more frequency channels to disentangle the CMB polarization signal from those of polarized galactic foregrounds.

4 List of the interested scientists in the community

Involved people in Argentina:

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5 Current status and expected challenges

The QUBIC instrument is currently undergoing its phase of laboratory calibration of its technological demonstrator version. A single focal plane with 236 TES detectors operating at 130 GHz and an array of 64 back-to-back horns along with a smaller optical combiner have been integrated into the final 1K box and cryostat. The horns array include the individual switches that enable the auto-calibration procedure. The cryogenic system has been successfully cycled and tested to reach the expected performance.

An image of the synthesized beam at various frequencies has been successfully measured in several bolometers in the focal plane of the technological demonstrator, using the laboratory calibration source. As an example, in Fig. 6 we show a comparison between the predicted synthesized beam at 150 GHz and the one measured in one of the TES. The left panel displays the measurement, and the right panel shows the expected shape without aberrations (geometrical optics). The signal is normalized to the maximum value in each of the maps. There is some degree of saturation in the simulated image, to mimic what is observed in the measurement. Albeit only qualitative, the agreement shown here constitutes good evidence of the successful performance of the instrument design. A quantitative characterization of the response of all detectors will be reported elsewhere, after the calibration of the technological demonstrator is completed. More details on the simulation of the optical beam combiner and horns array can be found in [46].

Figure 6: Comparison between the synthesised beam measured with one of the TES in the technological demonstrator (left panel) and the predicted beam without aberration effects (right panel).

Project	Frequencies (GHz)	ℓ range	Ref.	$\sigma(r)$ goal (no fg.)	$\sigma(r)$ goal (with fg.)
QUBIC	150,220	30–200		6.0×10^{-3}	1.0×10^{-2}
Bicep3/Keck	95, 150, 220	50–250	[18]	2.5×10^{-3}	1.3×10^{-2}
CLASS *	38, 93, 148, 217	2–100	[20]	1.4×10^{-3}	3.0×10^{-3}
SPT-3G †	95, 148, 223	50–3000	[19]	1.7×10^{-3}	5.0×10^{-3}
AdvACT ‡	90, 150, 230	60–3000	[21]	1.3×10^{-3}	4.0×10^{-3}
Simons Array	90, 150, 220	30–3000	[22]	1.6×10^{-3}	5.0×10^{-3}
SO (SAT) **	27, 39, 93, 145, 225, 280	30–300	[23]	1.3×10^{-3}	3.9×10^{-3}

* CLASS: Cosmology Large Angular Scale Surveyor; † SPT-3G: South Pole Telescope—3rd generation; ‡ AdvACT: Advanced Atacama Cosmology Telescope; ** SO (SAT)=: Simons Observatory Small Aperture Telescopes.

Table 1: Sensitivity of the main B -mode ground experiments operating in a frequency range similar to QUBIC. The label “fg” or “no fg” corresponds to the assumption on the foregrounds. Table extracted and expanded from [27, 28]. The entries for $\sigma(r)$ correspond to the estimates made in [37] for different experiments with the algorithms developed there (Appendix B1, no-delensing option). We acknowledge use of the public code CMB4CAST (<https://portal.nersc.gov/project/mp107>) for the computation of the last entry with the same method as in [37].

Furthermore, the angular resolution of the spectro-imager has been computed, and follows what is expected for the different subfrequency bands, namely, that the FWHM is reduced with increasing frequency.

After calibration is completed the TD will be shipped to Argentina for a first-light test on site in Alto Chorrillos. Meanwhile construction of the two complete focal panels at 150 GHz and 220 GHz, the full horns array and the final optical combiner will proceed. It is expected that the first module of the QUBIC instrument will be ready by 2020.

With two years of operation of its first module and an efficiency of 30% QUBIC is expected to be sensitive to values of the tensor-to-scalar ratio parameter r as low as 0.01. In Table 1 we summarise the expected sensitivity of QUBIC and other major ground-based experiments in the same frequency range, either running or expected to be deployed in the near future. It is important to notice that not only the reachable sensitivity should be taken into account, but also the systematic effects control and the possibility to remove foregrounds. In this sense, QUBIC has a unique status due to its particular architecture as a bolometric interferometer.

In the future, more modules at additional frequencies could be added, aiming at improving the foreground removal, and increasing the sensitivity to the primordial B -mode polarization of the CMB.

6 Timeline

We briefly describe the timeline of the instrument so far:

- 2010 → 2014: General design of the instrument.
- 2014 → 2016: Detection chain validation and detail design of the instrument.
- 2016 → 2018: Fabrication and test of sub-systems.
- 2018 → 2019: Delivery of sub-systems at APC, integration, tests.

Currently, December 2019, the fifth cooldown has begun, with improvements on the fridges, heat switches, HWP, thermalization of filters and damping of vibrations.

7 Construction and operational costs

The total costs so far (including the contributions of all the state members) have been the following:

- Hardware: 2.736.101,10 euros
- Travel: 101.173 euros
- Personnel: 1.068.881,60 euros
- Permanent personnel: 570.000 euros

8 Computing requirements

For the data analysis, several Tb of storage will be needed, which will be provided at NERSC computing center, where the final analysis will be performed.

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